

International Workshop

"Mountain Sustainability and European Development"

Hybrid – online & in-person

June 28, 2024, Rome, ITALY

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i>	08.45-09.15
Exploring Mountain Sustainability and Its Impact on Development	
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i>	09.15-10.45
Mountain Sustainability and Its Educational Implications for European Development	
Q & A	10.45-11.00
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – Humanity and Science in Mountain Regions</i>	
<i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i>	11.00-11.30
Humanity and Science: Shaping the Future of Mountain Regions	
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i>	11.30-12.00
Integrating Humanity and Science for Sustainable Development in Mountain Regions	
<i>Session 2 – Humanity and Science in European Mountain Regions</i>	
<i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences Austria</i>	11.00-11.30
Humanity and Science: Advancing Sustainability in European Mountain Regions	

<p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Exploring the Role of Humanity and Science in Promoting Sustainability in European Mountain Regions</i></p>	11.30-12.00
<p>Coffee break</p>	12.00-12.15
<p><i>Session 1 – Humanity and Science in Mountain Regions</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Connecting Humanity and Science for Sustainable Development in Mountain Regions</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Bridging Humanity and Science for Sustainable Growth in Mountain Regions</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p><i>Session 2 – Humanity and Science in European Mountain Regions</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Fostering Sustainable Growth in European Mountain Regions through the Integration of Humanity and Science</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Promoting Sustainable Development in European Mountain Regions: The Role of Humanity and Science</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p>Q&A</p>	13.15-13.45
<p>Concluding remarks</p>	13.45-14.00

Location: Rome Porta Maggiore, Via Casilina n.3, Roma, 00182, Italy